

THE UNIVERSITY OF BURDWAN

UNDERGRADUATE PROJECT

***RAMANUJAN'S SUMMATION :WHICH
CONTRADICTS THE TRADITIONAL SENSE***

**SURI VIDYASAGAR COLLEGE
DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS**

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-: TOPIC OF THE PROJECT :-

RAMANUJAN'S SUMMATION :

WHICH CONTRADICTS THE TRADITIONAL SENSE

-:ABSTRACT:-

Applied Mathematics & Theoretical Physics are the most important things to study about the nature.

"The beauty of Mathematics lies to solve all hidden secrets of our world"

The summation of all natural numbers must be a positive number but the topic of this project is how the value is

$(-1/12)$ which contradicts the traditional sense . In the other hand without this result the Earth can't expand, the Casimir Force will not act . Even we can't stand on the Earth surface if the result is not equal to $(-1/12)$

Application of this is indispensable for Space Science & Higher Mathematical Research . We can say that where there is application of physical significance of the world there is use of $1+2+3+\dots\infty = (-1/12)$

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RAMANUJANS SUMMATION WHICH CONTRADICTS THE TRADITIONAL SENSE

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-: INTRODUCTION:-

***“What on earth are you talking about?
There’s no way that’s true!”***

It has been pointed out to me that when I talk about sum’s in this article, it is not in the traditional sense of the word. This is because all the series I deal with naturally do not tend to a specific number, so we talk about a different type of sums, namely Cesàro summations . For anyone interested in the mathematics, Cesàro summations assign values to some infinite sums that do not converge in the usual sense. “The Cesàro sum is defined as the limit, as n tends to infinity, of the sequence of arithmetic means of the first n partial sums of the series.

Here I deal with the concept of countable infinity, a different type of infinity that deals with a infinite set of numbers, but one where if given enough time you could count to any number in the set.

**SO , LET’S SEE HOW AMAZING THE FACT IS
&
HOW MUCH IT’S IMPORTANT TO US**

How AMAZING it is :-

What will be the result if we add all positive terms from 1 to Infinity (∞) ?

It must be positive Infinity (∞). But no . It will be $(-1/12)$
If anyone is listening this for the first time then they will be shocked.

Ramanujan's First Notebook Page no.-60

ISN'T IT AMAZING !!

Great Indian
Mathematician
Srinivasa Iyengar
Ramanujan proved it
on his First notebook
on page no 60 and also
sent a letter to
Godfrey Harold
Hardy on 27th

February 1913. Reading which Hardy & Littlewood told him

“LUNATIC ASYLUM”

Traditional Sense :-

In generally if we add all the positive integral numbers from 1 to infinity then we must get a positive integer as a result .

But no it's fully opposite .

As a result we get (-1/12)

i) If we add all the positive numbers it will be positive Infinity (∞)

i.e.

$$1+2+3+\dots (\text{to } \infty) = \infty$$

ii) We also studied that $\sum_{n=1}^n n = \frac{n(n+1)}{2}$

Since here $n=\infty$. therefore it will be positive Infinity (∞)

i.e.

$$1+2+3+\dots(\text{to } \infty) = \infty$$

iii) $1+2+3+\dots$ the series has n^{th} term is n .

Therefore $p=1$

Therefore $\sum n$ is divergent by p-series test.

By p-series test we know if $p < 1 \rightarrow$ then convergent

&

if $p \geq 1 \rightarrow$ then divergent

Although the above results states that the series will be divergent

but the actual result is giving a finite negative value i.e $(-1/12)$

NOW LET WE SEE HOW IT IS $(-1/12)$

How it is $(-1/12)$:-

How far should scientists go in simplifying complexity to engage the public imagination? Boosted by a Dennis Overbye article in the *New York Times's Science Times* section, the youtube version of the video "ASTOUNDING: $1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + \dots = -1/12$ " had drawn well more than 1.5 million hits as of the morning of 4 February.

Colin Schultz

at *Smithsonian dot com*

expresses nonmathematicians' intrigued befuddlement:

So there you are living your life, content in your grasp on how the world works: up is up, down is down, the Sun rises in the east and sets in the west. Then, out of *nowhere*, a bunch of mathematicians try to tell you that the sum of all positive integers, that is, $1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + \dots$ and so on to infinity is equal to $\dots -1/12$.

Well, that's clearly ridiculous.

How can increasingly big numbers, when added together, make a small number!

How can whole numbers make a fraction!

How can positive numbers make a negative!

Tony Padilla and Ed Copeland, physicists at the University of Nottingham in the UK, appear in and narrate the eight-minute video. Minute by minute, what they explain requires from the viewer no mathematical grounding beyond simple addition and a smattering of the most basic algebra. But in the aggregate, what they argue goes well beyond that simplicity.

The way in which NUMBERPHILE proved how $1+2+3+\dots$ to ∞ is $(-1/12)$ is described below.

To prove it we have to introduce some new series named -

a) Grandi's Series :-

In Mathematics, the infinite series $1 - 1 + 1 - 1 + \dots$,

also written is sometimes called **Grandi's series**, after Italian mathematician, philosopher, and priest Guido Grandi, who gave a memorable treatment of the series in 1703. It is a divergent series, meaning that it does not have a sum.

However, it can be manipulated to yield a number of mathematically interesting results. For example, many summation methods are used in mathematics to assign numerical values even to a divergent series. For

example, the *Ceasaro's summation* and the *Ramanujan summation* of this series is $1/2$.

b) Basel problem :-

The **Basel problem** is a problem in mathematical analysis with relevance to number theory, concerning an infinite sum of inverse squares. It was first posed by Pietro Mengoli in 1650 and solved by Leonhard Euler in 1734, and read on 5 December 1735 in *The Saint Petesburg Academy of Science*.

The Basel problem asks for the precise summation of the reciprocals of the squares of the natural number, i.e. the precise sum of the infinite series :

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} = \frac{1}{1^2} + \frac{1}{2^2} + \dots = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$$

The sum of the series is approximately equal to 1.644934

The Basel problem asks for the *exact* sum of this series (in closed form), as well as a proof that this sum is correct. Euler found the exact sum to be $\pi^2/6$ and announced this discovery in 1735. His arguments were based on manipulations that were not justified at the time, although he was later proven correct. He produced an accepted proof in 1741.

MAIN PROOF :-

With the help of **Grandi's series** [**S=1-1+1-1+1-1+.....**] ; Great YouTube Mathematics channel 'Numberphile' had proved **Ramanujan's summation** in a simple way on January 2014

Which is as following:-

$$\begin{aligned} s_1 &= 1 - 1 + 1 - 1 + \dots \\ \Rightarrow 1 - s_1 &= 1 - (1 - 1 + 1 - 1 + \dots) \\ &= 1 - 1 + 1 - 1 + \dots \\ &= s_1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow 2s_1 = 1$$

$$\Rightarrow s_1 = \frac{1}{2}$$

Again, we construct a series named S_2 ,

$$S_2 = 1 - 2 + 3 - 4 + 5 - 6 + \dots$$

$$s_2 = 1 - 2 + 3 - 4 + 5 - 6 + \dots$$

$$2S_2 = 1 - 1 + 1 - 1 + \dots = S_1$$

$$S_2 = S_1/2 = \frac{1}{4}$$

Now we introduce the final and required series named S and doing the operation $(S - s_2)$ we get,

$$S = 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + \dots$$

$$s_2 = 1 - 2 + 3 - 4 + 5 - 6 + 7 - 8 + \dots$$

$$S - s_2 = 0 + 4 + 0 + 8 + 0 + \dots$$

$$= 4(1 + 2 + 3 + \dots)$$

$$= 4S$$

$$\Rightarrow S_2 = 3S$$

$$\Rightarrow -3S = s_2$$

$$\Rightarrow S = (-1/12) \quad [\text{Proved}]$$

This is not only the process to prove that the value of the

summation is $(-1/12)$

We can prove it with help of ζ function regularization.

The Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s)$ is a function of a complex variable $s = \sigma + it$. (The notation s , σ , and t is used traditionally in the study of the zeta function, following Riemann.)

Riemann had introduced

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = \frac{1}{1^s} + \frac{1}{2^s} + \dots \quad [\operatorname{Re}(s) > 1]$$

But to prove his own summation Ramanujan had look $S = -1$,

Where, $\operatorname{Re}(s) = -1$

Then, in this process we can see that $1+2+3+4+\dots \infty$ is $(-1/12)$

$$\zeta(s) = \frac{1}{1^s} + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \dots \quad [s \neq 1]$$

$$= \zeta(1-s) \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1-s}{2}\right) \pi^{\frac{1-s}{2}}}{\Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \pi^{\frac{-s}{2}}}$$

$$\therefore \zeta(-1) = \frac{1}{1^{-1}} + \frac{1}{2^{-1}} + \frac{1}{3^{-1}} + \frac{1}{4^{-1}} + \dots$$

$$= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + \dots$$

$$= \zeta(1+1) \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1+1}{2}\right) \pi^{\frac{1-1}{2}}}{\Gamma\left(\frac{-1}{2}\right) \pi^{\frac{1}{2}}}$$

$$= \zeta(2) \frac{1 \cdot \pi^{-1}}{-2\sqrt{\pi}\sqrt{\pi}}$$

$$= \frac{\pi^2}{6} \cdot \frac{0!}{-2\sqrt{\pi} \cdot \sqrt{\pi} \cdot \pi}$$

We know,

$$n \Gamma n = \Gamma(n+1)$$

$$\text{if, } n = -\frac{1}{2}$$

$$\therefore -\frac{1}{2} \Gamma\left(-\frac{1}{2}\right) = \Gamma\left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)$$

$$\Rightarrow -\frac{1}{2} \Gamma\left(-\frac{1}{2}\right) = \sqrt{\pi}$$

$$\Gamma\left(-\frac{1}{2}\right) = -2\sqrt{\pi}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{\pi^2}{6} \cdot \frac{1}{-2\pi^2} \\
&= -\frac{1}{12} \text{ [proved]}
\end{aligned}$$

By

Basel's Problem

$$\zeta(2) = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$$

CUT OFF REGULARIZATION :-

A cut off function can smooth the series while arrive to $(-1/12)$ at the Y- intercept . It is the bridge from Riemann-Zeta regularization to reliance on complex analysis , from Ramanujan Summation to shortcut of Euler Maclaurin smoothed version in $\sum n f(n/N)$

The smoothed curve will behave asymptotic to $(-1/12)+CN^2$ where C is constant & depends f

The original problem in number theory, that of *partition of a number* has a rich history. The problem is - given a positive integer n, a partition is a way to write it down as a sum of positive integers. For example for 10, one partition is 6+4. One is interested in finding out all possible ways of doing it for a number.

Let us pick a small number, say 4. Then it is clear that there are 5 ways of doing it. (4, 3+1, 2+2, 2+1+1 and 1+1+1+1). Note that the order is not important, that is, 1 + 1 + 2 and 1 + 2 + 1 are the same partition. We use the notation P(n) to represent

the number of partitions of an integer n . Thus $P(4) = 5$, similarly, $P(7) = 15$.

If we were to start enumerating the partitions for larger numbers, even for small numbers such as 10 we start seeing that there is a combinatorial explosion! To illustrate this consider $P(30) = 5604$ and $P(50) = 204226$ and so on. (btw, partitions can be visualized by Young tableau!).

Consider for a the moment the celebrated Prime number theorem which gave an asymptotic formula to get the number of primes that were there below a number x . It was only an approximate formula (the numbers it gave were not completely accurate and had error) but even then it was considered a great achievement as it uncovered a hidden structure in the primes. (The partition problem can be considered an "additive" analog to that of obtaining primes factors in which the primitive operation is multiplication).

A similar search was on for asymptotic formulae for the partition number $P(n)$ and because of the combinatorial explosion an accurate formula was considered difficult. Ramanujan believed that he could come up with an accurate formula even though it was considered extremely hard, and he came close. Along with Hardy he was able to give such a formula and it was noted by Hardy as one of his most important works.

The formula is:

$$P(n) \sim \frac{1}{4n\sqrt{3}} \cdot e^{\pi \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2n}{3}}}$$

This formula was remarkably accurate, for example for $p(1000)$, the error was about 1.4%. A similarly high number at that time

was verified by hand and it took about a month (I think it was $P(200)$ and the error was about

0.04%). This result was subsequently improved by Rademacher.

This asymptotic formula is something that is certainly useful in statistical and nuclear Physics like mentioned earlier in which such calculations are commonplace

One can proof that this smoothed sum is asymptotic to $(-1/12)+CN^2$, where C is a constant.

That depends on f. The constant term of the asymptotic expansion doesn't depends on f. It's obviously the same value given by the analytic $(-1/12)$.

My view about it:-

1)

As I was also belonging to the traditional sense (which is also not wrong), firstly when I show it I was also shocked .But I became curious about this fact and studied a few about it, and belived that it's a interesting topic to study which has two different types of correct result.

I became more curious about this fact after watching a video in YouTube (Channel Name:-blackpenredpen) on which the video creator also proved that it's also $(-1/8)$ in two different ways.

As following:-

NOW,

$$S=1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+10+\dots\infty.$$

$$\Rightarrow S=1+(2+3+4)+(5+6+7)+(8+9+10)+\dots \infty.$$

$$\Rightarrow S=1+9+18+27+\dots\infty.$$

$$\Rightarrow S=1+9(1+2+3+\dots\infty);$$

$$\Rightarrow S=1+9S;$$

$$\Rightarrow S=(-1/8)[\text{Proved}].$$

Again,

$$S=1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+10+11+12+\dots\infty$$

$$\Rightarrow S=1+2+(3+4+5+6+7)+(8+9+10+11+12)+\dots \infty$$

$$\Rightarrow S=3+25+50+\dots\infty$$

$$\Rightarrow S=3+25(1+2+3+\dots\infty);$$

$$\Rightarrow S=3+25S;$$

$$\Rightarrow S=(-3/24);$$

$$\Rightarrow S=(-1/8).[\text{Proved}]$$

Intersting to note that it's not giving only two or three different results.

We can prove it in many different ways by taking odd terms as in brackets and we will get that's square as common .

Such as 7 numbers in brackets then 49 (1+2+3+...) which also give us the result (-1/8) .

2)

Primarily , the whole proposition is useless in common logic and application as it is imperative that positive numbers added together should sum to a higher positive number. This result opposes both of these claims.

But , sometimes I feel that the beauty of mathematics is richened much by the techniques used and not the result. The reason is that sometimes results can be generalised to make many more replicates but a technique stays unique and different.

The techniques Ramanujan used were impeccably stunning and the mere logic and the effort he put into the calculations would be commendable.

Thus , I express dissent on there being not so many practical uses and acceptances of this beautiful argument.

3)

I myself concluded after days of research on the way it is proved in which the proof uses certain series in the proof its kinda mind bogalling.

In the proof we use the series $Sé = (1-1+1-1+1.....)$ which if drawn using 2d graph and putting 2nd axis to the time or every next unit like think of 1 on y axis is value at x axis 0 if y on unit 2 which is negative 1 then it will again be on 0 next on 1 then on 0 and so on till infinity so we see the axis of gravity(i

know where the hell come physics but let's be it for a moment) it will be on middle of 0 and 1 and that will be $1/2$ which coincidentally be the sum of infinite series of the series S^{\wedge} .

Now if we visit the second series $S^{\wedge} = (1 - 2 + 3 - 4 + 5 - 6 + 7 - 8 + 9 \dots)$ Here if we draw the similar graph of y axis and x axis it will create a point of gravity to $(1/4)$ or $(-3/4)$ depending on the infinity as either it ends on last digit as adding or subtracting the nth term n is the last term in the series .

There after we find the last series of the solution which is natural number so while adding or subtracting the S^{\wedge} to N series will just change the weight distribution of the S^{\wedge} series leading to the equation solution to be either $(-1/12)$ or $(1/4)$.

4)

According as formula of divergent series we can't shift or add any term in case of divergent series .

But Numberphile had done this in all of the three steps.

5)

Riemann has introduced & shown that Analytic condition of Analytic function is unique & zeta s will converge to a sensible value while $\text{Re}(s) < 1$

So, it says that $(-1/12)$ is a possible value of that series .

Applications in Higher Mathematics:-

1. In Bosonic String Theory it's being used to compute the possible energy level and, particularly the lowest energy level in a string.

2. Again, it's used in Casimir force for a scalar in one dimension . In Casimir force all the rest constants are totally $(-1/12)$,where the negative sign reflects the fact that the Casimir force is attractive.

It also says that , the universe is expanding

3. A similar calculation is involved in 3D ,using Epstein-zeta function in place of Reimann- Zeta function.

4. It has been used for calculation of electric force between two uncharged plates in vaccum(Casimir Effect). Also used in string theory.

5. It applies to quantum field theory: for a suitable system, Ramanujan summation removes a counter-term in a physically sensible manner, and provides renormalized results. In particular, it predicts a force, which has now been experimentally measured, but let us begin with a toy model.

6. In Quantum Physics there will be no energy between two uncharged metallic plates which is (zero point energy)

But, if $1+2+3+\dots$ (to ∞) = ∞

then there will be infinite energy. Which is practically & according to nature is impossible and it will be possible zero point energy if

$$1+2+3+\dots \text{ (to } \infty) = (-1/12)$$

Which is satisfying the nature's law.

Application Of Ramanujan's Summation :-

The Ramanujan summation is a technique used in number theory to assign a meaningful value to divergent infinite series. It is particularly useful in the study of prime numbers and the distribution of their values. Some examples of problems where the Ramanujan summation has been used include analyzing the distribution of twin prime numbers and the distribution of prime numbers in arithmetic progressions. Additionally, it has been used in the study of the Riemann zeta function and its zeroes, which are closely related to the distribution of prime numbers.

1. Ramanujan's mathematical findings have had numerous real-world applications in fields such as physics, computer science, and cryptography. For example, his work on partition functions has been used in statistical mechanics to study the behavior of atoms and molecules. In addition, his discoveries in number theory have been used to develop algorithms for computer encryption and data security. Ramanujan's legacy continues to inspire mathematicians and scientists today, and his contributions to the field of mathematics are still being studied and applied in various ways.

My Points of View:-

1. I also studied that according as N.H.Abel's concept we can't shift or add any term in the case of divergent series, which had done by Numberphile to proof Ramanujan's summation in all three steps.

2. Again the Reimann-Zeta function is applicable for $\text{Re}(s) > 1$, but to proof Ramanujan's summation we took $S = -1$.

Reimann-Zeta function fails to converge if $\text{Re}(s) < 1$. But Reimann had shown that the Analytic Continuation of Analytic Function is unique and also shown that the power series
$$\zeta(s) = \frac{1}{1^s} + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \dots$$
 converges to a sensible value.

3. Quantum mechanics says that there is no energy between two uncharged metallic plates (Zero Point Energy).

But it shows that there will be ∞ energy between the plates if the series $(1+2+3+4+\dots\infty)$ is divergent, which is impossible.

And interestingly if we put $(1+2+3+4+\dots\infty)=(-1/12)$ then there will be no energy between the two plates, which is similar with the experimental Idea.

4. In complex analysis , analytic continuation is a technique to extend the domain of a given analytic function . Analytic continuation often succeeds in defining further values of a function for example in a region where an infinite series representation in terms of which it is initially defined becomes divergent.

My Education :-

After studying this the thoughts came to my mind that can the sum of all positive numbers be negative??, If either it be $(-1/12)$ or $(-1/8)$, but both of them fails the closure law.

- If we think with the reality that's practically happens in nature, then the result of the summation of this series will puzzle us and if we think with our primary idea that will also be true by concept of Pure Mathematics, and which is the traditional Sense.*
- Therefore, in conclusion we can say, that the reality which is similar to the experimental idea, though puzzles us but it will help us to reveal the Universe.*

So we can say that "The beauty of Mathematics lies to solve all hidden secrets of our world"..

- So I am very curious about this fact and I am at beginner level, I have studied a little bit about this and I will try to*

fulfill my concept about this strange result which have both character convergent and divergent, and also used both results according as the similar experimental idea.

- Till now as much I have studied I came to an conclusion that both of the traditional sense and the calculated value [either $(-1/12)$ or $(-1/8)$] are true as the the sum of all the infinite terms be not unique or not fiinite then the series be called divergent series. And the series (whatever may we get the results) we took was divergent.*

-:Conclusion:-

In this project work I learn about *Ramanujan Summation which contradicts the Traditional sense* & it's proof, application in Mathematics , various field of our life & the contradictions etc.

This project work has helped me to know deeply about the topic & to clarify its concept.